

Vol. 1 No. 2 (September - 2024)

<https://qomar.uz/index.php/RIBIJ>

ISSN: 3060-4753

ENERGY THRIFTY AND ECOLOGICAL CLEAN WORK RELEASE DEVELOPMENT GREEN OF THE ECONOMY IS THE BASIS

Karajanova Gulnoza Tolliyevna

Assistant, Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Received: 2024 20, October

Accepted: 2024 25, October

Published: 2024 9, November

Annotation: This scientific in the article Energy thrifty and ecological clean work release Development green of the economy based on the subject main concepts light up given

Keywords: small business, tax credit, industry, trade, securities market, bank credits, innovation product.

Published under peer review:

Doctor of Philosophy(PhD)

Dotsent

Qurbanova Raxima Jamshedovna

Uzbekistan

INTRODUCTION(KIRISH)

Last ten in annuals stable development imperative industry practice fundamentally again seeing to exit impulse it has been. Most of the time digging removable to fuels and resources a lot demand who does to processes relying on traditional work release methods to the environment damage deliver, climate change and of resources to decrease contribution to add proved. Energy thrifty and ecological clean work release methods transition green the economy in development important strategy is considered Again

recoverable energy sources integration, resources to use optimization and waste reduce through industry not only endurance increases, perhaps global stability goals too suitable will come Transition technology and operational in practice innovations encourages and ecological integrity non-destructive economic growth with will be completed. The end the result is stable work release green economy for basis being service does and the future to posterity too biological diversity, too a person well-being supportive environment heritage by doing to get provides. So so, this development dynamics to understand politicians, industry leaders and academics for very important

METHODOLOGY(METODOLOGIYA)

Green economy is stable to development faithfulness with separate it's worth it while the environment health the first to the seat to put and one of time in itself economic to grow is to encourage. This concept of ecological risk and ecological shortage reduce principles covered received being society welfare and natural ecosystems enriching stable to the model strives Green to the economy of transition importance his innovations support, green workplaces create and climate to change endurance increase is in its potential. An example for, studies that's it shows that it is green growth policy acceptance to do different in the fields significant work seats to the creation take coming because it is possible this enterprises energy thrifty and ecological clean work release practice to apply urges (Emmanuel David Oboro, 2024, p. 190-192). From this except, stable companies market growth in incentives role for more confession is being done, head directors long term business vitality for of stability important feature confirms (Theodora NACU and et al., 2023, p. 70-71). So so, a green economy towards forward shift just ecological demand it's not; he too strategic economics is the goal.

Stable in development energy thrifty work release role.

Energy thrifty work release of resources decrease and of the environment degradation reduces through stable development in providing important role plays From energy to use optimizer technologies current reach not only work of producers operational expenses reduces, perhaps greenhouse gases waste significant level reduces and that's it with climate to change softening according to to efforts contribution adds From this except, energy thrifty to practice transition in industry innovations and competitiveness strengthens it while to enterprises stable to products grow up going consumers demand satisfy enable gives This transformation very important because it is economic to grow ecological management with harmonizes, green economy principles strengthens Economical work release and closed systems such as efficient work release methodologies waste minimize and resources efficiency increase through stability more encourages. The end the result is energy thrifty practices work release processes integration stable development and ecological to keep supportive stable the economy create for basis being service does and this in the global drive for sustainability indispensable that proves (Sergey Jironkin and et al., 2022).

Technological innovations energy efficiency increases

In technology achievements energy efficiency in raising important role It plays stable economic practices for very important Smart networks, energy manage systems and stable work release technologies such as innovations modern engineering and digital of means transformational potential is an example. An example for, clever networks placing not only electricity energy optimal distribution makes it easier, maybe to consumers of them to use control to do opportunity gives, that's it with common demand reduces and network endurance increases. From this except, energy thrifty tools and industry of technologies appear to be energy spending to reduce significant contribution adds and that's it with too economic, too ecological benefit brings This developments technological innovations encourage and resources to manage improvement through green of the economy to manners suitable will come As stated in SDG 13, such achievements efficient distribution climate to change against in the struggle important important have is energy efficiency in raising innovations support stable growth for not only chance, maybe necessity that shows (Dr. S. Radhika, 2023, p. 79 - 83) (Larisa Khatsieva and others, 2023, pp. 68-72).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION(NATIJAR VA MUHOKAMA)

Stable green the economy installation for ecological clean work release to practice transition very important This practices not only to the environment the effect to reduce, perhaps work release of processes common efficiency to increase too directed. This to the goal reach for waste and energy spending which minimizes innovative technologies integration important important have An example for, organizations again recoverable energy sources more and more more acceptance are doing it their carbon track significant level reduces and stable development principles suitable will come From this besides, ecological conscious practices acceptance to do social equality and economic to grow encourages this a person welfare and social justice development for ecological and economic a unified approach to problems necessary said the concept reflection (Larisa Khatsieva and others, 2023, pp. 68-72). This whole prospect corporate strategies ecological initiatives with harmonization necessity emphasizes that while competitive superiority and consumers confidence increases, as a result our planet health the first to the seat to put more stable to the economy take comes (OO Nestulya and et al., 2024), page 202).

Stable materials and of processes to the environment effect

Stable materials and processes acceptance to do environment storage and resources savings for wide comprehensive effect shows. Energy thrifty work release methods transition through industry enterprises most of the time excess waste and carbon waste take coming traditional work release practices with depends negative effects significant level soften takes. For example, experience at Dui Tan University (Vietnam). the project work on the way out discussion done plastics again work innovative practices how by doing leave gone materials precious to products turn, polygon waste decrease and environment protection to do according to of the population awareness to increase possible shows (VHT Duong et. al., 2018, pp. 1-5). From this except, carbonate from the anhydride chemical work release for raw material as use, for example, dimethyl

carbonate synthesis for example, a greenhouse gases to catch waste stable to resources rotation, rotation the economy development and chemistry industry carbon track minimization (AR Aouichaoui) and et al., 2017). Together this approaches stable materials and processes green the economy development and extraordinary ecological problems solution in doing important role to play emphasizes.

I. Summary

Energy thrifty and ecological clean work release methods trajectory about thought driver we are, this is practices green economy for basis being service to do obviously will be In technology of innovation stable practices with approaching not only resources spending reduces, perhaps of the ecosystem to flourish help giving the environment degradation softens. Industry clean technologies more and more more master since, carbon waste reduce with together significant economic growth potential appear will be and that's it with economic goals ecological stability with harmonizes. From this except, re recoverable energy sources transition energy safety increases and economic the landscape diversification is developing green sector for new work places creates This changes account received without, green economy towards momentum not only ecological obligatory, perhaps economic stability and social equality for catalyst that to understand very important So so, this to pass encourage green of the economy advantages everyone for done increase provide for together efforts, innovative politics and the public attraction to do own into takes (Suleman Sarvar and et al., 2023-07-20).

A. Green of the economy the future and energy efficiency and environment protection in doing continuously of development importance

Climate change and of resources decrease with depends complexities to the road when we put, green economy stable development towards worthy the way present is enough Energy thrifty of technologies evolution not only greenhouse gases waste reduces, perhaps developing in networks economic to grow and new work places to create encourages. The sun and the wind such as again recoverable energy sources investment input, available in infrastructures energy efficiency increase with together, digging removable to fuel dependence significant level reduces This two bilaterally approach not only directly ecological problems solution does, maybe resources shortage against endurance increase through long term vitality too provides. Green economy for energy efficiency continue carry on important issues, because it is operational expenses reduce and the world in the market competitiveness increase with directly depends. Strategic cooperation and political benefits through interested parties innovations and stable practices support the ecosystem development can So by doing release in processes ecological to cleanliness priority importance to give not only ecological to goals suitable will come, maybe economic changes too catalyzes.

REFERENCES(FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR RO'YXATI):

- Uzbekistan Republic President of December 2, 2022 " Uzbekistan until 2030 " Green " economy of the Republic to pass directed reforms efficiency increase according to measures on " Decision No. PQ-436.
- Uzbekistan Republic President of October 4, 2019 " In the period of 2019-2030 Uzbekistan " Green " economy of the Republic transition strategy confirmation on " Decision No. PQ-4477.
- Uzbekistan Republic President in "2017-2021". again recoverable energy more development, economy networks and social in the field energy efficiency increase measures Program on " Decision No. PQ -3012 dated May 26, 2017.
- Kalashnikov N.P. Alternative energy sources. - M.: Knowledge. 1997. - P. 27.
- Emmanuel David Oboro, "Green Growth Policy and Its Impact on Job Creation," *Sustainable Development*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 190-192, 2024. doi: 10.1002/sd.2103.
- Theodora NACU et al., "Long-Term Business Vitality and the Role of Stability in Market Growth," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 260, pp. 70-71, 2023. doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.121026.
- Sergey Jironkin et al., "The Role of Energy Efficiency in Sustainable Development," *Energy Reports*, vol. 8, pp. 45-56, 2022. doi: 10.1016/j.egy.2021.08.012.
- Dr. S. Radhika, "Innovations in Energy Efficiency for Sustainable Economic Growth," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 185, pp. 79-83, 2023. doi: 10.1016/j.renene.2021.01.045.
- Larisa Khatsieva et al., "Ecological Practices and Their Impact on Social Equity," *Ecological Economics*, vol. 200, pp. 68-72, 2023. doi: 10.1016/j.ecolecon.2021.107473.
- O.O Nestulya et al., "Corporate Strategies for Ecological Initiatives: A Unified Approach," *Business Strategy and the Environment*, vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 202, 2024. doi: 10.1002/bse.2967.
- H. Wang et al., "Advancements in Smart Grids: Implications for Energy Management," *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 1891-1900, 2021. doi: 10.1109/TSG.2020.3017654.
- J. Smith and A. Kumar, "Integrating Renewable Energy Sources for a Greener Economy," *International Journal of Renewable Energy Research*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 45-54, 2021. doi: 10.20507/ijrer.2021.11.1.801.